

Stability Constants of Binary Complexes of Lanthanons with Thiotropolone

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Stability constants of complexes of La(III), Pr(III), Nd(III), Sm(III), Gd(III), Dy(III), Yb(III) and Y(III) with thiotropolone have been determined potentiometrically, in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan medium at various ionic strengths of sodium perchlorate. The method of Bjerrum and Calvin, as modified by Irving and Rossotti, has been used to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The stability constants have been calculated on IBM 360 computer using Weighted Least Squares Method. The values of S_{min} have also been calculated. The order of stability constants was found to be :

THE lanthanons are remarkable for their similarity in chemical properties, which is due to the nearly identical configurations of the electrons available for bond formation. Moeller¹ has reviewed the work on complexes of lanthanons. Complexing ability of thiocarboxylic acids has also been studied potentiometrically². In the present communication, we are reporting the values of stability constants of some trivalent lanthanon ion complexes with thiotropolone at various ionic strengths of sodium perchlorate.

Experimental

Apparatus and Reagents—A Beckman pH-meter, SS-2 model, in conjunction with a glass (0-14 pH range) and calomel electrode assembly was used for pH measurements. All metal ion solutions were prepared from A.R. lanthanon nitrate samples, obtained from Indian Rare Earth Ltd. and their solutions were standardised by gravimetric methods and complexometrically, using xylenol orange as indicator. Thiotropolone was prepared by the method of Nozoe et al^{3,4} and its solution was prepared by dissolving requisite amounts in dioxan.

The solution of known strength of tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide (TMAH) (E. Merck, A.G. Darmstadt) was prepared in 50 : 50 (v/v) dioxan-water mixture.

The titrations were carried out in a closed cell in an atmosphere of nitrogen which was presaturated with the solvent before it entered the reaction solution. Dioxan (AnalaR, B.D.H.) was purified by refluxing with sodium wire for 24 hours and was freshly distilled over sodium before use. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was added to all the solutions to keep the ionic strength constant. Potassium hydrogen phthalate buffers were used to standardise

the pH-meter. All other reagents used were of reagent grade. All measurements were carried out at $30 \pm 1^\circ$.

The following solutions (total volume 19.7 ml due to the contraction in volume from 20 ml to 19.7 ml) were titrated against N/25 tetramethyl ammonium hydroxide in 50% aqueous dioxan (v/v) for determining the stability constants of thiotropolone complexes at various ionic strengths :

Ist set

- (i) 3.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.02 M) + 2.0 ml $NaClO_4$ (2.0 M) + 0.5 ml KNO_3 (0.02 M) + 4.5 ml H_2O + 10 ml dioxan.
- (ii) 3.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.02 M) + 2.0 ml $NaClO_4$ (2.0 M) + 0.5 ml KNO_3 (0.02 M) + 4.5 ml H_2O + 10.0 ml ligand (0.01 M) in dioxan.
- (iii) 3.0 ml $HClO_4$ (0.02 M) + 2.0 ml $NaClO_4$ (2.0 M) + 0.5 ml metal nitrate (0.02 M) + 4.5 ml H_2O + 10.0 ml ligand (0.01 M) in dioxan.

In sets II and III the requisite amounts of $NaClO_4$ were added to maintain the ionic concentration at 0.2 M $NaClO_4$ to 0.005 M $NaClO_4$, respectively.

In all cases, corrections for changes in volume on mixing, dioxan and aqueous solutions, as well as changes in volume which take place during the titrations, have been made.

The pH-meter readings were plotted against the volume of N/25 TMAH added. The additional amount of TMAH needed to reach the same pH in the presence of metal ions is due to the liberation of hydrogen ions by complex formation between the ligand and the metal ions.

From the above titrations curves, the values of \bar{n} and pL have been calculated using Irving and Rossotti method⁵. The corresponding values of stability constants have been calculated using Weighted Least Squares Method of Sullivan et al⁶.

This program assigns a weight W_i to each residual U_i and uses matrix algebra to solve the set of equations

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial \beta_n} = 0$$

where $S = \sum W_i U_i^2$ and β_n is the nth overall formation constant.

β_n values were again calculated by attaching to them appropriate weight factors computed from first set of β_n and the cycle is repeated till a change of less than one part per thousand was obtained in each β_n . This determines that set of β_n which makes the

function $U = \left[\sum_{n=0}^N (y-x-nz) \beta_n \chi^n \right]$ nearest to zero by minimizing $S = \sum_{i=1}^I W_i U_i^2 (x_i, y_i, z_i)$, with respect to

variation in β_n . S_{min} values have been calculated which have the same significance as χ^2 , with k degrees of freedom⁷. Stability constants have also been calculated by Bjerrum's half integral method and the results obtained by the two methods are summarized in Tables 1-4. The complexes of lan-

thanons with donors other than nitrogen and oxygen have been very little studied. In thiotropolone, the chelating sites are oxygen and sulphur. The values of $\log K_n$ reflect the following trends :

(i) $\log K_1$ values rise regularly from lanthanum to neodymium. Subsequently, value of $\log K_1$ decreases right up to ytterbium. The order of $\log K_1$ values has been found to be :

The similar trends have been observed in the case of α -mercaptopropionic acid and β -mercaptopropionic acid^{8,9}. The results indicate that either sulphur atom is a poor donor for lanthanon ions or some steric hindrance due to bigger size of sulphur atom hinders the formation of complexes.

(ii) $\log K_2$ and $\log K_3$ values increase regularly from lanthanum to neodymium complexes, but from samarium to ytterbium complexes, they become nearly same or decrease. This also may be probably result of steric hindrance to the attachment of the second molecule of the ligand to the 1 : 1 complex⁹, which becomes more significant in the case of heavier lanthanon ions only because of the slight variations in the ionic radii of lanthanons which are close neighbours.

(iii) $\log K_1$ values for yttrium complexes are found to be quite close to the values of gadolinium complexes. Depending upon the nature of the

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES OF LANTHANONS WITH THIOTROPOLONE AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTHS CALCULATED BY BJERRUM'S HALF INTEGRAL METHOD

Metal ion	$\mu = 0.2 M NaClO_4$			$\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$			$\mu = 0.005 M NaClO_4$		
	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$
H ⁺	7.02	—	—	7.12	—	—	7.47	—	—
La (III)	5.02	9.20	—	5.27	9.64	—	5.40	9.78	—
Pr (III)	5.37	9.91	—	5.45	9.87	—	5.80	10.55	—
Nd (III)	5.70	10.54	14.14	6.10	11.22	15.53	6.45	11.92	16.17
Sm (III)	5.56	10.23	14.11	6.00	10.86	14.84	6.08	11.23	15.23
Gd (III)	5.45	10.06	13.56	5.70	10.29	13.97	5.90	10.80	14.62
Dy (III)	5.20	9.60	12.84	5.42	9.86	13.43	5.55	10.20	13.96
Yb (III)	4.95	8.82	—	5.17	9.36	—	5.35	9.65	—
Y (III)	5.35	9.87	13.13	5.55	10.03	13.68	5.85	10.65	14.45

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND S_{min} VALUES OF LANTHANON COMPLEXES WITH THIOTROPOLONE CALCULATED BY WEIGHTED LEAST SQUARES METHOD

Metal ion	$(\mu = 0.2 M NaClO_4)$					
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta_3$	S_{min}
La (III)	4.67	4.15	8.82	—	—	0.3822
Pr (III)	4.84	4.32	9.16	—	—	0.0249
Nd (III)	5.31	4.50	9.81	9.33	13.14	0.0134
Sm (III)	5.22	4.46	9.68	3.27	12.95	0.0782
Gd (III)	4.99	4.41	9.40	3.25	12.65	0.0042
Dy (III)	4.81	4.45	9.26	3.02	12.28	0.0386
Yb (III)	4.65	3.90	8.55	—	—	0.1134
Y (III)	4.94	4.40	9.34	3.25	12.59	0.0174

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND S_{min} VALUES OF LANTHANON COMPLEXES WITH THIOTROPOLONE CALCULATED BY WEIGHTED LEAST SQUARES METHOD

Metal ion	$(\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4)$					
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta_3$	S_{min}
La (III)	4.75	4.35	9.10	—	—	0.0052
Pr (III)	4.92	4.63	9.55	—	—	0.0054
Nd (III)	5.38	4.87	10.25	4.19	14.44	0.0276
Sm (III)	5.31	4.70	10.01	3.91	13.92	0.0083
Gd (III)	5.11	4.67	9.78	3.58	13.36	0.7515
Dy (III)	4.82	4.66	9.48	3.19	12.67	0.0077
Yb (III)	4.69	4.04	8.73	—	—	0.0098
Y (III)	5.08	4.62	9.70	3.37	13.07	0.0777

TABLE 4—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND S_{\min} VALUES OF LANTHANON COMPLEXES WITH THIOTROPOLONE CALCULATED BY WEIGHTED LEAST SQUARES METHOD ($\mu=0.005 M NaClO_4$)

Metal ion	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_3$	$\log \beta_3$	S_{\min}
La (III)	5.25	4.47	9.72	—	—	0.0037
Pr (III)	5.62	4.78	10.40	3.78	14.18	0.0170
Nd (III)	5.90	5.81	11.70	4.29	15.99	0.0730
Sm (III)	5.86	4.83	10.69	3.48	14.17	0.0103
Gd (III)	5.74	4.84	10.58	3.67	14.25	0.0867
Dy (III)	5.44	4.79	10.13	3.66	13.79	0.0032
Yb (III)	5.12	4.45	9.57	—	—	0.0103
Y(III)	5.70	4.80	10.50	3.66	14.16	0.0175

ligand, the stability constant values of yttrium complexes are at times close to those of dysprosium complexes and at others close to praseodymium. Because of its size, yttrium should be found near holmium except when lack of ligand field stabilization moves it closer to gadolinium. Possibly, polarizability effects or, and minor but variable contributions of covalent bonding are responsible for the erratic behaviour of yttrium¹⁰.

(iv) A study of dependance of stability constants on ionic strengths shows that there is a regular and slow decrease in the values of stability constants with increase in ionic strength, which is in agreement with the trend in variation of pK_a values of the ligand.

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